

ISic3017

I.Sicily inscription 3017

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2013.10.02

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Buscemi

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50160

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332326

1. [— — — — —]ελ [— —]
2. [— — — — —]ΟΙ [— — —]
3. ΚΛ. [— — — — —]ΟΛΙ [— —]
4. ΚΛΙΔΙΙΜ [— — — — —]
5. [— — — — —]ΟΥ [— — — —]
6. vac. Ὀρτυξ Λ [— — — —]
7. vacat Ε [— — — —]
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645365

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Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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